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Simulation of temperature profiles using an anatomically correct human model

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Introduction

Mathematical models of human thermoregulation have been mainly based on a simplified model of the human body where cylinders represent body and layers represent tissues. Advancement in medical imaging presents a unique opportunity to improve human thermoregulatory models by providing accurate representations of body geometry and composition (3). The purpose of this paper is to simulate temperature profiles of the human body using a torso model developed from medical images.

Methods

The torso model is from an “average” human male, 37 years old, 1.76m in height, 81kg in mass, and 22.7% body fat. The structure includes: skin, muscles, heart, liver, lungs, kidneys, stomach, intestines, fat, bone, and bladder. This model spans from the top of the shoulders to below the pelvis. The XCAT phantom data set from Duke University (1) was segmented and processed in Simpleware ScanIP (Synopsys, Mountain View, CA) to create meshes suitable for finite element analysis. Heat transfer simulations are conducted using finite element analysis software (COMSOL, Burlington, MA). The tissue biophysical properties, such as metabolic rate, blood flow rate, and heat conductivity, are taken from the literature (2). Heat balance within the body is described by the following equation:

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \lambda T + M + \omega_b c_b (T_b - T)$$

where ρ is tissue density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), c is the tissue specific heat ($\text{J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$), T is temperature (K or $^{\circ}\text{C}$), t is time (s), λ is tissue thermal conductivity ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$), and M is metabolic heat production ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$). The term $\omega_b c_b (T_b - T)$ refers to convective heat exchange with blood flow, where ω_b , C_b and T_b denote blood flow rate ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$), blood specific heat ($\text{J}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) and blood temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), respectively. The boundary condition at skin surface is defined by:

$$-\lambda \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = (h_c + h_r) \cdot (T - T_a) + E$$

Where h_c is convective heat loss coefficient ($\text{W}\cdot^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}\text{m}^{-2}$) and h_r is radiative heat loss coefficient ($\text{W}\cdot^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}\text{m}^{-2}$), T_a is ambient temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), and E is basal evaporative heat loss ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$).

Results and discussion

Spatial temperature distributions in Fig.1 show that tissue temperatures vary with location. Spatial temperatures in central tissues vary at different locations, such as heart, bladder and rectum. This indicates that “core temperature”, which is an important parameter for thermal physiology, varies with measurement location. Even in the rectum, the temperatures vary as measurement depth changes, from $\sim 36.8^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 37.4°C . Heart temperature, which would be similar to esophageal temperature, is $\sim 37.4^{\circ}\text{C}$. The skin temperature ranges from $\sim 30.9^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 33.5°C and its mean is $\sim 32.9^{\circ}\text{C}$. These values are consistent with the values measured from a human body in thermal neutral conditions.

Conclusions

Simulations can reveal detailed temperature profiles that are difficult to obtain with traditional measurement techniques. Thus, this methodology, by combining medical images and finite element analysis, provides a modern approach to advancing the field of thermophysiology.

Fig.1 Temperature distribution at thermal neutral conditions

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